

The Role of Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Decision-Making of Civil Society

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of civil society in decision-making processes and the importance of legal awareness and legal culture. Civil society influences decision-making processes through public participation and active citizenship within the framework of the principles of democracy and the rule of law. Legal awareness can inform citizens about their rights and duties, and legal culture can further develop this awareness and increase respect for laws in society. The article examines the role of education, mass media and civic activism in the formation of legal culture.

Keywords: Civil society, Decision-making, Legal awareness, Legal culture, Democracy, Civic activism, Mass media, Education.

Civil society is an environment organized by socially, economically and politically active citizens, non-governmental organizations and other structures. The role of this society in the decision-making process is important because it encourages citizens to participate in state and public affairs. Citizens can express their opinions and participate in decision-making processes, which further enhances democratic processes. Civil society allows to monitor the activities of state and administrative bodies. This, in turn, reduces corruption and abuses. As part of civil society, the media plays an important role. They highlight events in society, inform citizens and encourage discussion. Legal awareness is important in informing citizens about their rights and responsibilities. Providing legal knowledge to citizens through the education system helps to protect their rights. It is important to organize public events, seminars and forums for the development of legal culture. Civil society plays an important role in the decision-making process because it encourages citizens to be active and protects their rights. The development of legal awareness and culture ensures effective participation of citizens and strengthens democratic societies.

The role of legal consciousness is very important in the decision-making of civil society. Legal consciousness is the level of understanding and acceptance of legal norms, laws and their importance by citizens and members of society. In a society with high legal consciousness, citizens know their rights and are ready to protect them. This allows active participation in democratic processes, that is, elections and other activities. Citizens, understanding their rights and obligations, actively participate in making fair decisions in society. Through the influence of this legal consciousness, decisions are more in line with the interests of society. When legal consciousness is strong, citizens exercise mutual social control, which helps prevent corruption and lawlessness. Education and dissemination of information are important to increase legal awareness. Clarification of laws, rights and obligations encourages citizens to participate more actively and consciously in the life of

society. In this way, legal consciousness plays an important role in ensuring the development and stability of civil society.

The following areas are important for the development of legal awareness: Teaching legal knowledge in schools and higher education institutions. Conducting special courses and seminars. Covering legal topics through mass media, informing citizens. Organization of various events, forums and seminars by civil society organizations to promote legal knowledge. Legal awareness is an important concept that helps citizens understand their rights and duties. Its development serves the strengthening of civil society, increase of legal culture and strengthening of democratic processes. The process of improving legal culture requires a multifaceted approach. Enhancing legal culture through education, mass media, public events, and encouraging civic engagement serves to ensure justice, order, and stability in society. This, in turn, helps to strengthen democratic values and increase legal awareness among citizens.

Legal awareness informs citizens about their rights and duties, encourages them to actively participate. In this process, citizens will have the opportunity to express their opinions, ensure justice in society and influence the state administration. Legal culture plays a key role in increasing respect for laws, adherence to legal norms, and strengthening social order. To promote legal culture, it is important to impart legal knowledge to citizens through education, mass media and public events. As a result, the development of legal consciousness and culture increases the stability of civil society and the effectiveness of democratic processes. Thus, citizens will contribute to the formation of a just and peaceful society by realizing their rights and duties, actively participating, and obeying the laws.

Literature used

1. Назаров Қ.Н. Аксиология қадриятлар фалсафаси. -Т.: “Маънавият”, 1998.-121 б.;
2. Yo.S.Sadikova. Huquqiy ongni shakllantirishda demokratik qadriyat- larning oʻrni. (Monografiya). T.: «Innovatsion rivojlanish nashriyot- matbaa uyi», 2021. - 128 b.
3. Исломов З.М. Давлат ва ҳуқуқ назарияси. — Г.: “Адолат”, 2007. –Б.537.
4. Дмитриев О.А.. Правосознание и правовая культура. / Теория государства и права. Под. ред. Пиголкина. -Москва: Юрайт-Издат, 2006. -С.547.
5. Головистикова А.Н. Правосознание и правовая культура. Проблемы теории государства и права. -Москва: Изд. ЭКСМО, 2005. -С.658.
6. См.: Теория государства и права. Под. ред. проф. Ромашова Р.А. – СПб.: Изд. Асланова Р. Юридический центр Пресс, 2005. -С. 346.
7. Проблемы общей теории права и государства. Москва: Изд. Группа. НОРМА-ИНФРА, 2004. – С.396-384.
8. Одиториев Х.Т. Фуқаролик жамиятининг моҳияти ва қадриятлар тизими. / Ўзбекистонда фуқаролик жамиятини шакллантириш: муаммолар ва ечимлар. Илмий-амалий анжуман материаллари. – Тошкент: ТДЮИ, 2004. – Б.28.
9. Неновски Н. Право и ценности: Пер. с болг. / Под ред. Зорькина В.Д. -М.: Прогресс: 1987. -С.33;
10. Азизхўжаев Л.А. Эркинлаштириш давр талаби. //Жамият ва бошқарув. - Тошкент, 2000. -№1. -Б. 6;